

THE ROLE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN WORLD CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Abstract. *There are many phraseological units of an inter-style nature, and their number is constantly growing. However, there are still fewer of them that phraseological units limited in their use to a certain sphere of communication. This is explained by the fact that the overwhelming majority of phraseological units, equivalent in semantics to a word, function in Russian language as figurative synonyms of words and have some kind of "lowered" or "elevated" expressive-stylistic coloring.*

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Classification of phraseological units. The whole set of phraseological units is classified according to a variety of features.

One of the classifications involves dividing phraseological units into groups according to general grammatical features. The following groups are distinguished below.

1. Nominal phraseological units. In a sentence, they perform the functions of the subject, predicate, and complement (for example, a light hand, a snake in the grass, golden mountains).

2. Verbal phraseological units. Phraseological units of this group play the role of a predicate in sentences (for example, to wet one's throat, to remember, to drive out of patience).

3. Adjectival phraseological units. They have the meaning of a qualitative characteristic, act in a sentence as a definition or a nominal part of the predicate (for example, to be on one's own mind, in the girls).

4. Adverbial phraseological units. This group includes phraseological units that characterize the quality of an action and act as circumstances in a sentence (for example, reluctantly, without memory).

5. Interjectional phraseological units. They express the will, feelings, act as separate undivided sentences (for example, Neither fluff nor feather! God help you!) [1, p. 97].

There is a classification of phraseological units based on their origin. In this case, there are originally Russian phraseological units, which include:

1) common Slavic phraseological units that have correspondences in other Slavic languages (for example, naked as a falcon);

2) East Slavic phraseological units that have correspondences only in the Ukrainian and Belarusian languages (for example, neither kola nor dvora);

3) actually, Russian ones, which do not have such correspondences, since they arose directly in Russian language (for example, in all Ivanovo). [1, p. 100].

The second group is borrowed phraseological units, among which the most notable are "phraseological units borrowed from the Old Church Slavonic language, mostly biblical (e.g. daily bread, tower of Babel, crown of thorns)" [1, p. 101]. In addition, there are borrowings from ancient mythology (Achilles' heel, Pandora's box), as well as phraseological units that came from European languages at a later time (for example, the phraseological unit the princess and the pea

(meaning “an overly pampered person”), widely used in modern Russian, comes from the fairy tale of the same name by G.H. Andersen). Some phraseological units are tracings from other languages (e.g. blue stocking - from English “blue stocking”; kill time - French “tuer le temps”). However, the most famous and widespread classification was proposed by academician V.V. Vinogradov [5]. It is based on the varying degree of idiomaticity of the components in the phraseological unit. “This classification assumes the division of phraseological units into phraseological combinations, phraseological fusions and phraseological unities” [5, p. 41]. This is a classification based on the semantic fusion of components.

1. Phraseological combinations. They necessarily contain a word that has a secondary, phraseologically related meaning. Words that play the role of a mandatory context most often appear in the basic meanings: sleeps and sees (meaning “passionately wants something, dreams of implementing something”), with one’s own eyes (meaning “directly by oneself, without intermediaries (to see)”, etc. Each word has an independent meaning, but one of the words is used only in this combination (“bosom friend”), or one of the words is used in this meaning only in this combination, while in free phrases it has a different meaning (“blank verse”) [5, p. 107].

2. Phraseological unities. This group includes metaphorical turns of phrase in which the internal form and motivation for the meaning of the original combination are well understood. For example, henbane ate too much (meaning “went crazy”), seven Fridays in a week (meaning “someone often changes their decisions, intentions, moods, etc.”), like two drops of water (meaning “completely, very strongly (similar, etc.)”), a snake in the grass (meaning “an evil, insidious, dangerous person”), etc. The meanings of phraseological units can be understood figuratively from the meanings of their components [5, p. 108].

3. Phraseological fusions. These are idioms in narrow sense of the word, in which the motivation is lost, i.e. is not realized by ordinary native speakers; for example, to engrave on the nose (meaning “to firmly remember”). These are indecomposable phrases, the meaning of which cannot be deduced from the meanings of their components. Phraseological fusions also include phraseological units containing obsolete words or grammatical forms (“a byword”, “without a doubt”) [5, p. 109].

In addition to all the above-mentioned groups of phraseological units, N.M. Shansky distinguishes another group – phraseological expressions (Modern Russian Language 1981: 77-78). These include such turns of phrase that are always reproduced as ready-made lexical units with a constant lexical composition and grammatical form. These are quotations, aphorisms, proverbs, sayings, catchphrases. Shansky distinguishes between phraseological expressions of a communicative nature and phraseological expressions of a nominative nature. The former includes predicative combinations equal to a sentence: A person – it sounds proud; A nightingale is not fed with fables, etc. The latter include combinations of words identical only to certain parts of a sentence: labor successes, warmongers, etc.

Stylistic neutral and colored phraseological units

Based on the scope of use of phraseological units of the modern Russian literary language and their inherent expressive features, N.M. Shansky and V.V. Ivanov divide them into three large categories: colloquial, literary, and inter-style phraseology.

1. Phraseological units of a colloquial nature. “Phraseologisms of a colloquial nature differ from inter-style phraseologisms, on the one hand, in a narrower scope of use (they are

predominantly or exclusively used in oral speech), and on the other hand, in their specific “reduced” expressive-stylistic coloring” [13, p. 67].

These properties are especially clearly visible when comparing them with commonly used words: “to talk” – “to chat”.

Almost all colloquial phraseological units have a figurative character and bring a touch of ease and simplicity to speech.

2. Phraseological turns of a bookish nature. “Phraseological turns of a bookish nature differ from colloquial and everyday phraseological turns, on the one hand, in a completely different sphere of use (they are used primarily or exclusively in written speech), and on the other hand, in their specific “elevated” expressive-stylistic coloring (bookishness, solemnity, pathos, poetry, etc.)” [13, p. 69].

Like book vocabulary, the main sphere of use of bookish phraseology is strictly standardized literary speech, the styles of journalistic and scientific works, the language of fiction, etc.

Therefore, the most striking groups among bookish phraseology are phraseological turns of a terminological, poetic and journalistic nature. The special qualities of bookish phraseological units (as well as colloquial and everyday phraseological units) are most clearly felt when they are compared with commonly used lexical synonyms: “surrender” - “lay down arms”.

3. Inter-style phraseological units. “Inter-style phraseological units are understood as stable combinations of words known and used in all styles of language and, as a result, representing phraseological units with a “zero” stylistic characteristic” [13, p. 70], for example: “keep your word”.

Inter-style phraseological units, like inter-style words, are simple names of phenomena of objective reality, without any evaluation of them. They are not colored expressively and are commonly used. Therefore, in a series of synonymous words and phrases, they always appear as stylistically neutral (“he went crazy” - “not all at home”).

There are many phraseological units of an inter-style nature, and their number is constantly growing. However, there are still fewer of them that phraseological units limited in their use to a certain sphere of communication. This is explained by the fact that the overwhelming majority of phraseological units, equivalent in semantics to a word, function in the Russian language as figurative synonyms of words and have some kind of “lowered” or “elevated” expressive-stylistic coloring.

In the process of speech activity, children often encounter situations when it is necessary to describe a person, object, action in the most figurative and expressive way, to give an evaluative characteristic. This is exactly what phraseology is needed for.

Phraseologisms are ready-made figurative means that are widely used both in ordinary conversational communication and in works of art, where they, along with the author's metaphors and other tropes, are a figurative form of expression. Successful study of the functional role of phraseologisms in the language of the writer, their life in a work of art and the identification of the very nature of phraseological units is largely facilitated by their analysis in the texts of works with which children become familiar in elementary grades in Russian language, reading, and speech development lessons.

But can younger students successfully learn phraseological units, are they ready to use them in their speech? J. Piaget outlined the age limit for children to learn phraseological units —

from 11-12 years old, during the period of development of associative, formal operations in the child. However, experimental observations show that children aged 6-7 years “are already able not only to understand, but also to use individual phrases that are understandable to them” (O.F. Miroshnichenko 1986). During the experiment conducted by O.F. Miroshnichenko, children in the senior group of a kindergarten (5-6 years old) were able to understand and explain more than half of the phraseological units offered to them.

When studying phraseological units in primary school, one can rely on the following provisions:

1. Phraseological units should be understandable to younger students.
2. Correspondence of phonetic, syntactic, and stylistic features of phraseological units to the grammatical material studied in primary school.
3. It is necessary to take into account the stylistic coloring of phraseological units [6, p. 21].

The study of phraseological units is an integral part of the work on speech development, the definition of the content and methodology of which is now given much attention due to the low level of speech development of children. The speech of our students is often characterized by low expressiveness, inappropriate, imprecise use of language means. Therefore, it is necessary to teach younger students not only the correct, but also the appropriate choice of language means when constructing their own statements.

At school, the corresponding work should be aimed not only at acquiring certain knowledge, but also at developing children's linguistic sense, linguistic intuition, and at accumulating positive speech experience. In particular, working with phraseological units and introducing them into child's vocabulary will contribute to achieving these goals.

Working with phraseological units stimulates speech development. But is it only speech that develops in the process of this work? It is known that thinking develops in unity with speech development. Thinking is improved in speech communication. Therefore, working on developing clear, correct, expressive speech, the teacher simultaneously develops schoolchildren's thinking, raising it to a qualitatively new level. Working on stable combinations of language contributes to the formation of the ability to abstract, and abstraction is a constructive component of students' mental activity, since generalization and formation of concepts occur on its basis. Etymological examination of phraseological units, finding the true source of each image will help lay the foundations of research activities, which cannot but be useful to children in their further education.

"The problem of assimilation of phraseological units by primary school students in Russian language lessons has not yet found a proper solution: principles for the selection of phraseological material have not been developed, there is no verified list of phraseological units recommended for assimilation by younger students, there are very few relevant articles and manuals. Familiarization of younger students with stable combinations occurs in a practical way in the process of working on exercises and texts in Russian language and literary reading lessons" [4, p. 37].

When studying phraseology at school, a scientific approach is necessary. Knowledge of phraseological units and the phraseological units themselves should be understandable to younger students. "In order for students to be able to use phraseological units in their speech, in order for schoolchildren to be able to speak briefly and accurately, figuratively and expressively, work on

enriching the active phraseological stock of students must be carried out systematically and consistently" [4, p. 41].

Assimilation, use of figurative expressions (phraseological units) is impossible without their conscious assimilation. Knowing the meaning, explanation of phraseological units, younger students will use them in their speech. The greatest effect of assimilation can be achieved by using visual aids when explaining the meaning of figurative expressions.

An analysis of modern textbooks shows that the authors provide for assignments and exercises on phraseology to a certain extent, but in general the work is episodic and mainly comes down to interpreting the meaning of phraseological units.

An exception are textbooks that present a system for teaching phraseology to younger students in Russian language.

Teaching phraseology in the textbooks of A.V. Polyakova consists of the following interconnected and interdependent elements: enriching students' vocabulary with phraseological units, clarifying and activating it, assimilation by students of the concept of a phraseological unit and developing the ability to use a phraseological dictionary. The author describes in detail the methodology for working with phraseological units in the methodological recommendations for the teacher [6, p. 12]. Let us dwell on the most important, significant elements of the system from the standpoint of teaching phraseology to younger students.

In accordance with the general methodological principles of the system of L.V. Zankov the definition of the concept of phraseological unit is introduced already in the first grade and is consolidated in the second. Familiarization with the concept of "phraseological unit" and its assimilation contributes to a clearer recognition by younger students of this linguistic unit among others. Researchers Shevlyakova E.D., Valchuk E.V., developing a methodology for phraseological work in primary school, recommended replacing the term "phraseological unit" with the phrases "figurative expression", "figurative phrase" [4, p. 36]. As a result of this approach, students find it difficult to differentiate phraseological units from metaphors and phrases that include epithets, personifications and other tropes. And most importantly, the categorical feature of a phraseological unit - stability - remains without the attention of younger students. In the definition presented in the textbooks of Polyakova A.V., it is stability that is the leading feature of a phraseological unit.

One of the main areas of work throughout the initial course of Russian language is enriching students' speech with phraseological units. The textbooks by A.V. Polyakova present various methods of explaining the meaning of phraseological units. Most of the methods stimulate independent search by students: the meaning of a phraseological unit is clarified by a picture-illustration, the meaning is established during the analysis of a number of phraseological units and ready-made interpretations presented to them in any order, the search for a phraseological unit by its meaning or the meaning is clarified by a phraseological dictionary. Picture-illustrations on the plots of famous works of children's literature, exercise texts containing information about the origin of phraseological units not only help to establish the meaning, but also contribute to the awareness of their figurative, metaphorical component. In order to activate the vocabulary of younger students and their use of phraseological units in their own texts, the following training exercises are provided: composing sentences and texts with the specified phraseological unit, selecting phraseological units on a specific topic or corresponding to the main idea of the text, selecting and writing down phraseological units that act as key phrases to the text. As a technique

aimed at developing figurative speech in younger students, it is recommended to use a comparison of sentence variants with a phraseological unit and a synonymous word.

The textbook "Russian Language" for the 4th grade contains an educational phraseological dictionary, the construction of which is based on the thematic principle of the arrangement of phraseological units. This approach to compiling a dictionary has an important methodological and didactic value: it expands the understanding of younger students about the emotional and expressive possibilities of phraseological units, stylistic coloring, synonymous and antonymous connections of these linguistic units; allows using a thematic group of phraseological units when working on texts of a certain topic and content.

Thus, the analysis of modern textbooks on the language for primary school shows that the authors provide for assignments and exercises on phraseology in one volume or another, and phraseological units act as linguistic material when studying spelling and other topics.

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